

Building Capacity for Nursing Research and EBP in Non-Magnet Hospitals

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Background

- Magnet accreditation serves as a hallmark of excellence for nursing practice.
- Only 6% of hospitals in the United States have achieved Magnet status (ANCC, 2016).
- Despite the growth of Magnet designation program over the past 30 years, it is difficult to achieve Magnet accreditation that is tied into improve nursing care, improve patient safety culture, improve patient outcomes, and overall job satisfaction.
- Hospitals undertaking the journey toward Magnet designation must build research and evidence-based practice (EBP) infrastructure that support the translation of research and EBP into clinical practice.

Problem Statement

Among the Magnet principles, the evidence suggests that it is difficult to achieve the domain of “New Knowledge, Innovations, and Improvements” due to financial constraints, limited access to partnerships with public universities, and limited expertise in the area of research knowledge and practices.

Purpose

- The primary objective for this Doctor of Nursing Practice (DNP) project is to conduct a thorough review of the literature and to evaluate relevant data to support the successful implementation of the Magnet principle of New Knowledge, Innovations, and Improvements.
- The secondary objective of this project is the development of practice guidelines to support building nursing research capacity, practicing evidence-based nursing care, and developing nursing innovations.
- The practice guideline will recommend a step by step approach that will involve the establishment of a nursing research council, the design of the role, and planning of a support system to disseminate nursing research and EBP.

The Five Forces of Magnetism

- **Transformational Leadership**
A transformational leader can articulate goals and communicate high expectations that strategically align with the organizational mission, vision, and values to improve institutional performance. In this form of leadership, nurses should perceive their voices are heard, their input is valued, and their practice is supported.
- **Structural Empowerment**
Magnet recognized organizations involve nurses in decision-making roles at all levels. Nurses engage in shared governance, and council structure to establish clinical practice guidelines and address opportunities for improvement.

Figure 1 The New Model for ANCC's Magnet Recognition Program. 2009 American Nurses Credentialing Center

- **Exemplary Professional Practice**
Exemplary professional practice focuses on excellence, collaboration, quality, safety, and best evidence-based practices. The exemplary professional practice is defined as a schematic description of a system, theory, or phenomenon that depicts how nurses practice, collaborate, communicate, and develop professionally to provide the highest quality care for those served by the organization (ANCC, 2015). Exemplary professional practice is the final product achieved by professional nurses.

- **New Knowledge, Innovations, & Improvements**
Within the context of the magnet model, New Knowledge, Innovations, and Improvements components encompass the following categories *research*, *EBP*, and *innovation* that focus on quality improvement.

According to Stevens (2013), to affect better patient outcomes, convergence of new knowledge must be translated into clinically useful methods and must be implemented effectively across the spectrum of health care team within a system context, and must yield measurable and meaningful impact on performance and health outcomes.

- **Empirical Outcomes**
Empirical refers to a measurable outcome that has been validated by data to show that actual change has occurred because of a particular action (ANCC, 2015). Magnet designation primarily focuses on structure and processes, with an assumption that good outcomes will follow (Smith, 2014). Empirical outcomes begin with pre-contemplated data collection that an organization can use to ascertain an area that needs improvement.

Theoretical Framework & Application of ACE Star Model to Practice

- **Discovery of New Knowledge**
A main purpose of research is to address clinical issues and to assist in practice change. There are few knowledge focused triggers that can be used to provide the trends in standard of care of the healthcare organization, providing transparency to the consumers. The use of various knowledge focused triggers will aid in identifying health care issues that need improvement.:
 Clinical Quality Indicators
 National Agencies
 Organizational Standards and Guidelines
 Philosophies of care

Figure 2. ACE Star Model of Knowledge Transformation Sample. Adapted with expressed permission by Kathleen R. Stevens, Ed.D., RN, ANEF, FAAN. Copyright 2015, Stevens.

- **Evidence Summary**
During this phase, the NRC can engage members to participate in research synthesis activities related to patient care, conducting a critical appraisal of meta-analysis, and integrative reviews, or review of the literature on clinical topics that will aid in disseminating EBPs. The use of Cochrane Collaboration Databases of Systematic Reviews can provide evidence to support specific clinical research to improve patient safety and outcome.

- **Translation into Guidelines**
For EBPs to be successfully adopted and sustained, system leaders, policy makers, and stakeholders must buy-in to the benefits of research Leadership support must be secured to build the nursing research infrastructure. The Magnet Recognition Program has been the catalyst in EBP adoption, using it as a marker of excellence. The translation of evidence summaries can be achieved through pilot studies, development of clinical practice guidelines, clinical pathways, protocols, and algorithms (Cohen et al., 2010).

- **Practice Integration**
Evidence-based practices must be disseminated throughout the hospital for a full translation into practice. The NRC should coordinate quarterly meeting through Nursing Grand Rounds, Nursing Forums, poster presentations, newsletters, staff meetings, journal publications, and periodic roundtable discussions (i.e. Journal Clubs) to disseminate EBPs across the continuum of care.

- **Process, Outcome Evaluation**
The final phase of the ACE Star Model focuses on evaluation. In EBP, outcomes are evaluated to assess consistency, establish generalizability across participants, treatment variations, or settings, and to improve true reflection of reality that reduces bias. Evaluation of EBP can be measured through patient health care outcomes (i.e., readmission rate, falls), provider and patient satisfaction (i.e., HCAHPS, Press Ganey), and health care cost analysis.

Evidence-Based Model

*Will need to collaborate with PhD nurse researcher

Recommendations

- In the absence of an in-house research expert, the leadership must identify an external expert who is willing and able to help the organization achieve its nursing research goals.
- The ideal candidate must hold doctoral degree and be affiliated with a university. University affiliation will provide access to resources that are not available at a hospital setting.
- The doctoral nurse researcher must possess extensive research and publishing experience.
- Once a doctoral prepared nurse is contracted, the organization can establish a hospital-wide Nursing Research Council (NRC) as one of the key concepts of shared governance to create avenues for carrying out research studies.
- The last recommendation is to secure executive leadership support. This can streamline access to hospital infrastructure for research. Also, these leaders can put research initiatives in the context of the hospital's mission.